

What is controlled vocabulary ?

A control vocabulary could be defined as a specially prepared word and sentence list. This list is applied for expressing information in an orderly coherent manner. Additionally, at times, it is known by the term controlled language.

Controlled vocabularies are used Academic research, government organization ,medical and health care etc. Also controlled vocabulary can help to solve Homographs, Synonyms, variations in spellings, misspellings, reducing ambiguity, increasing findability, and improving the performance of information retrieval system.

Controlled vocabulary subject heading, taxonomies, thesaurus, LCSH, MeSH etc. are examples.

What is the need of control vocabulary in IR ?

Controlled vocabulary has five purpose-

Translation - it is a tool that aids in the process of changing the natural language used by authors, indexers, and users into a specific vocabulary that can be efficiently used for indexing purposes as well as retrieval activities.

Consistency - actively promote and advocate the creation of consistency, not only in the form of the terms but also in the meticulous, step-by-step assignment of the terms.

Label and browse- Labeling and navigation are important elements of any navigation system; they offer consistency and clearly define hierarchies that help the user locate easily the content object that one is looking for.

Indication of relationship- semantically indicate the kind of semantic relationship present among the term

Retrieval – an important searching tool that helps users find relevant content objects.

what are the tools of vocabulary control ?

Subject heading - Controlled vocabulary includes the use of one single specific term to describe only that subject. Indeed, this methodology regarding controlled vocabulary has an enhancing effect on user searches, making it not only easier but also remarkably accurate in the results brought to the searcher.

Thesauri- . A thesaurus is a specimen of controlled vocabulary, specifically used in the process of information retrieval to help clarify semantic ambiguities and uncertainties that occur during the process.

LCHC- It is a classification scheme widely used in all types of library cataloging systems irrespective of the institutions or organizations involved.

MeSH – MeSH is type of control vocabulary. it is helps to search medical and health

related information.

Taxonomy – Taxonomy is a kind of controlled vocabulary. iasset tagging

What is classaurus ?

Classaurus is a complex and structured faceted hierarchical thesaurus, which includes several vocabulary control features. This complex system consists of a set of terms each of which has different schedules of hierarchies which correspond to the Elementary Categories which are Discipline, Entity, Property, and Action. Besides these basic categories, there are also their respective Species or Types, besides Parts and Special Modifiers that further subdivide and specify the terminology.

Classaurus is a vocabulary control tool, especially developed with a focus on effective management of linguistic resources. It was discovered by the very creative minds of Ganesh Bhattacharyya, who, among other uses, designed it for purposes associated with POPSI and the system of pre-coordinate indexing. Classaurus works as a faceted systematic scheme: this enables it to conduct a systematic hierarchical classification that also helps in better structuring, therefore better retrieving, of information.

Parts of classaurus –

1. The Alphabetical index part
2. A Systemaic Index Part

What are the dsifference between natural language and artificial language ?

1.Origination and evolution of ideas

Natural language develops with time through human communication. Natural languages are organic and have grown out of use for everyday conversations. For instance, examples would include English, Spanish, Chinese, or Hindi.

Artificial Language: Human beings have artificially created language for specific purposes, like logic, programming, or constructed languages for artistic or scientific communication. Such examples include programming languages like Python, or a fictional language like Klingon or Esperanto.

2. Purpose and Various Applications

It is through natural language that the wide range of communication people must conduct daily activities. It forms an important tool, through which people can communicate complex feelings, reflect subtleties of culture, and communicate a variety of concepts

essential to human life.

Artificial Language: Is usually used for a particular purpose or simply for a particular function. It can be applied, as programming languages, such as, JavaScript, which is an example: it is used in order to code for some applications while constructed language also called invented languages like the world of Esperanto, which was basically introduced for international communication.

3. Complexity

Highly complex and ambiguous. It is rich in slang, idioms, dialects, and irregular grammar, which makes it flexible but hard to standardize. Natural languages can be very subtle in their meanings and contexts.

As a concept, artificial languages are generally much more structured and precise than their natural counterparts, which usually have an element of ambiguity. One good example of this is in programming languages, which are constructed with very rigid syntax and grammatical rules to be followed so that machines will interpret and execute correctly. On the other hand, artificial languages are often devoid of the subtle expressions that can be found within natural languages, resulting in a more direct and obvious way of communicating.

4. The Topic of Grammar and Related Regulations

Natural Language encompasses a wide and diversified range of grammatical rules that can vary significantly depending upon geographical regions, cultural backgrounds, and other social contexts. Such grammatical rules are not at all rigid but instead show an amazing degree of flexibility, and it is quite common to find exceptions to these rules-for example, think of the irregular verbs in the English language.

Artificial language has well-defined and rigid rules that it does not deviate from. Take the case of programming languages for instance; without a semicolon, a major error might completely stop the execution process. On the other hand, natural languages are lenient, tolerate informalities as well as small mistakes and these are tolerated more in the case of casual conversation among speakers.

5. Change and Evolution

Natural Language: As time passes by, the natural language is perpetually and perpetually changing with the advent of new words and novel expressions, even the grammatical rules that form with the advancements of human societies and technology. It takes many years and occurs because of cultural, geographical factors and dominant social waves.

Artificial Language: These languages are typically modified by the creators or owners of the language or by various user communities interacting with the language. Such modifications are typically made with purpose and convey a well-defined, defined intent, such as an update to improve functionality or feature in a programming language.

6. The notations of flexibility and ambiguity:

Natural languages are greatly flexible and can amazingly reflect complex emotions, abstract concepts, rich shades of meaning which lie between straightforward expressions. While such is the flexibility inherent in the workings of natural languages, its opposite also prevails as meanings get quite ambiguously stated at certain places or even sometimes, as words could also prove ambiguous.

Artificial Language: Less flexible and typically not ambiguous. For instance, in programming, each instruction has one clear meaning, so the possibility of misinterpretation is reduced.